
Relationship between Teachers' Compliance to Requirements of Code of Conduct and Educational Output in Secondary Schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of teachers' compliance to the requirements of code of conduct on educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. The study was guided by three objectives and three research questions and four hypotheses. A correlational research design was adopted with a population of 1,927 teachers from 36 senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. The sample for the study was 331 determined by Taro Yamane formula and using a proportionate random sampling technique. The study employed two research instruments for data collection. The first was Teacher Registration Council Teachers' Professional Standard Assessment Scale. The second was Educational Output Scale. One was used to collect data on teachers' code of conduct while the other was used to collect data on educational output in terms of students' academic performance. The two instruments were faced and content validated by three experts. The internal consistency reliability coefficients were determined using Cronbach Alpha. This yielded an overall reliability coefficient of 0.86 for Teacher Registration Council Teachers' Professional Standard Assessment Scale and 0.88 for Educational Output Scale. A total of 331 copies of the instruments were administered while a total of 302 were retrieved and used for data analysis. Data gathered were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient for research questions and t-transformation for the hypothesis. The results showed a moderate, positive and significant relationship between teachers' professional knowledge, skills, membership obligations and educational output. The result further showed a positive, slightly high and significant relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school management should encourage teachers to be committed to professional obligations. This could be achieved by sponsoring teachers to conferences, seminars and workshops organized by professional bodies.

Keywords: Code of Conduct, Teachers' Code of Conduct, Educational Output, Teachers' Compliance to Code of Conduct.

Introduction

Teachers play important role in nation building. They are the architects of a nation's educational foundation. Furthermore, teachers impart knowledge, critical thinking skills, and values to students, which are essential components of an informed and responsible citizenry.

Through their dedication and expertise, teachers lay the groundwork for future doctors, engineers, scientists, artists, and leaders who will contribute to the growth and development of the nation (Patel, 2018). In addition to academics, teachers are instrumental in the moral and ethical development of students. They instill values such as honesty, integrity, tolerance, and empathy. A nation built on these values is more likely to promote harmony, justice, and social cohesion. Teachers act as role models, exemplifying these values in their own behavior, which leaves an indelible mark on the young minds they nurture (Mugbo, 2020; Musa, Jimba & Ogundele, 2015; Popovska & Popovski, 2021).

Teachers are catalysts for innovation and critical thinking. They encourage students to question, analyze, and develop creative solutions to problems. These skills are crucial for a nation's progress, as they empower citizens to adapt to changing circumstances, address complex challenges, and contribute fresh ideas to various sectors, from technology to policy-making (Musa, Jimba & Ogundele, 2015). Teachers have the power to promote social cohesion and inclusivity. They create inclusive classrooms where diversity is celebrated and differences are respected. In doing so, they teach the values of tolerance and acceptance, ensuring that future citizens are more likely to embrace diversity and work together for the common good. This sense of unity is vital for the stability and progress of a nation (Shevchenko, Dubiaha, Melash, Fefilova & Saenko, 2020).

Teachers have the responsibility of fostering civic awareness and engagement. They educate students about the rights and responsibilities of citizenship, encouraging them to participate in the democratic process. In this way, teachers empower individuals to become active and informed citizens who can contribute to the betterment of their nation through voting, advocacy, and community involvement (Zylfiu, 2014).

For these vital roles that the teacher plays in nation building, it is imperative that the teacher is guided in carrying out his/her duties. Such a guide would help the teacher in their conduct while executing their duties. To achieve this, the Nigerian Registration Council of Nigeria, TRCN has provided a code of conduct which specifies rules and regulations to guide teachers' practice in Nigeria.

The Teachers' Code of Conduct in Nigeria outlines the professional standards and ethical behaviors that teachers are expected to uphold. This code is intended to ensure that teachers provide a high-quality education and maintain a positive and safe learning environment for

students. The professional standards specified in the code of conduct cover professional knowledge; professional skills; professional values, attitude and conduct; professional membership and obligations; ethical behaviour (Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, TRCN, 2013). A brief description of these professional standards and behavior as specified in the code of conduct is presented in the sections that follow.

Professional Knowledge: Teachers are expected to possess knowledge of: the subject they teach, pedagogy, curriculum requirement, literacy and numeracy, application of modern computer systems and communication technology, socio-cultural, ethnic and religious backgrounds of students, how this background knowledge affect learning, stages of human development and how students learn (Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, 2010).

Professional Skills: Teachers are expected to possess skill in: planning learning programme, planning teaching and learning goals, selecting and organizing content for preparation of lesson notes, selecting instructional resources, use of instructional resources, effective classroom communication, student grouping, using appropriate teaching methods/strategies, conducting reliable assessment, conducting valid assessment, helping students based on assessment data, providing feedback to students, providing feedbacks to parents/guardians/other stakeholders, programme monitoring, record keeping, maintain law and order in accordance with international best practice, maintenance of safety and conducive learning environment, identifying students with special needs (e.g. gifted students) and collaboration (Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, 2010).

Professional Attitude and Conduct: Teachers are expected to: show respect for learners' right and dignity, demonstrate responsibility for educational programme, show empathy towards students, maintain confidentiality of students' personal information, shun sexual and related abuse of office, campaign against examination misconducts, abhor illegal students' groups, serve as role model to students, free of corrupt practices, contentment with legitimate income, avoid unacceptable disciplinary measures on students, put ideological beliefs under check when dealing with students, show respect for other teachers, demonstrate high level of integrity, show zero tolerance for social discrimination, avoid defaming other teachers, avoid touting (e.g. using unethical practices such as misinformation to take away client and or learners from colleagues). They are also to avoid canvassing (advertising) oneself, avoid copyright violation, settle disputes using professional mechanisms (e.g. Teachers Investigation Panel and court), inspire and motivate subordinates, demonstrate charismatic personality and objectivity in the discharge of

duty, demonstrate democracy in decision making, contributes to academic development. Teachers are supposed to be abreast with theory and practice of education around the world, ensure all round development of students, demonstrate respect for right of parents/guardians to the information on their ward. In essence, they should communicate regularly with parents/guardians, treat parents/guardians with utmost respect and avoid favours that may influence professional decisions, while they promote parent teacher association and activities. In practice, teachers are to be professionally independent (avoid contract agreements that may negatively affect the exercise of professional duties). Professionally, teachers are to stick to areas of professional competence, show respect for contract duly entered into with other parties and show respect for agreement reached between their unions and other parties, show good example of a good citizen in the society, apt to provide advice to parents and government on educational matters, be law abiding, demonstrate tolerance, demonstrate health personal habits, avoidance of acts of omission contrary to professional practice, avoidance of acts of commission contrary to professional practice, engage only in constructive criticisms based on high sense of responsibility, demonstrate open mindedness (Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, 2010).

Professional Membership Obligations: The teacher has some membership obligations. These include: getting membership with professional bodies such as TRCN. They are expected to pay annual TRCN subscription to possess up-to-date license, engage in internship after graduation, engage in self appraisal to ascertain need for capacity building, engage in continual improvement in professional competence, take advantage of professional development opportunities (e.g. through self-help, TRCN and other stakeholders, seek highest professional standards when dispensing duties, be committed to the teaching profession, be efficient in executing duties, show dedication to work, show loyalty to the teaching profession, contribute to the building of the community, demonstrate obedience to education law (Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria, 2010).

Educational output is a comprehensive term encompassing the results, achievements, and outcomes of an education system. It includes both quantitative and qualitative measures of educational success (Abari & Odunayo, 2012). Typical examples of educational output include: literacy and numeracy rates, graduation rates, academic performance/achievement, employability, research and innovations among others (Otoibhi & Ubani, 2020).

Literature shows that there exists a relationship between teachers' professional standards (code of conduct) and educational output in the school system. For example, in a study, Iroegbu and Uyanga (2019) found that professional ethics comprising: professional competence, professional integrity and professional accountability significantly predicted quality of educational output in federal universities, South-South Zone of Nigeria. In another study, Ayeni (2018) found a positive, slightly high and significant relationship between teachers' professional ethics and instructional performance of teachers in secondary schools in Owo Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria. Furthermore, Chukwu, Ezepue, Evelyn, Iremeka, Onyemaechi, Vivian, & Uwakwe (2020) found that teachers' professional ethics had a significant relationship with classroom management and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria. The present study sought to find out the influence of teachers' compliance to code of conduct on educational output in terms of students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt metropolis.

Statement of the Problem

In recent time, there has been reports of decline in the standard of education in Nigeria and this has been attributed among others to decline in teacher commitment and competencies (Duze, 2011). Decline in teacher commitment and competencies is capable of negatively affecting students' motivation, engagement, school culture and professional growth among others (Kumar, 2013). Could teachers' professional compliance to the requirements of code of conduct influence the educational output in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis? The present study aimed to provide answer to this question.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to find the relationship between the teachers' compliance to the requirements of code of conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. Specifically, the study intended to:

1. ascertain the relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.
2. determine the relationship between teachers' professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.
3. find out the relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

4. ascertain the relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Research Questions

The study provided answer to the following research questions.

1. What is the relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?
3. What is the relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?
4. What is the relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.
3. There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.
4. There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational design. The reason for using this design is because, the researchers intended to investigate the relationship between two variables which are teachers' compliance to requirements of code of conduct and educational output. A population of 1927 teachers from 36 schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis (Source: Rivers State Post Primary Schools Board). This number comprised 1,239 teachers from 20 schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area and 688 teachers from 16 schools in Port Harcourt City local government area. The sample for the study comprised 331 teachers determined using Taro Yamane formula ($n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$). Where, N = population = 1927 and e = significant level = 0.05. Proportionate

random sampling technique was adopted to achieve the sample size of 331. This resulted in randomly selecting approximately 213 teachers from Obio/Akpor and 118 from Port Harcourt City.

Two instruments were used for data collection. The first was Instrument used for data Teachers' Professional Standards Adapted from the Nigerian Teacher Registration Council Teachers' Professional Standard Assessment Scale (TPSAS) (Nigerian Teachers Registration Council, 2010). The instrument has four sections used to elicit data for Teachers' Professional Knowledge, Teachers' Professional Skill, Teachers' Attitude and Conduct; Professional Membership Obligations. The items were structured on a four-point rating scale of Poor (1 Mark), Fair (2 Marks), Good (3 Marks) and Excellent (4 Marks). Each section has a total of 5 items. So each section has a minimum score of 4 and maximum score of 20. The second instrument was a questionnaire titled: Educational Output Scale (EOS). This instrument was structure based on literature review. Students academic performance was used to measure educational output. The instrument has a total of five items used to elicit information about educational output in terms of students' academic performance. The items were also structured on a four-point rating scale of Poor (1 Mark), Fair (2 Marks), Good (3 Marks) and Excellent (4 Marks). So, the minimum score was 4 and the maximum was 20. The two instruments were subjected to face and content validity by three experts. One was a measurement and Evaluation Expert. The others were from Research and Statistics Department of TRCN.

Internal consistency was calculated for the two instruments using Cronbach Alpha. This yielded reliability coefficients of 0.81 for Teachers' Professional Knowledge, 0.78 for Teachers' Professional Skill, 0.83 for Teachers' Attitude and Conduct, 0.79 for Professional Membership Obligations and 0.86 for the entire TPSAS. The reliability calculation for EOS yielded reliability coefficient of 0.88. Based on these values, the instruments were considered reliable.

A total of 331 copies were administered and a total of 302 (91.2% return rate) copies were retrieved and used for data analysis. This comprised 203 from Obio/Akpor and 99 from Port Harcourt City.

The correlation coefficient obtained from Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to answer the research questions. The hypotheses were tested by testing the significance of r . This was achieved by converting calculated value of r (r -cal) to t -test statistics. The formula

for converting r to t according to Udoh (2003) is: $t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}}$, where r is the calculated coefficient of correlation, n is the sample size. This becomes the calculated value of t. This value is compared with the critical value of t at 0.05 level of significance and 300 (302-2) degree of freedom. If calculated value of t (t-cal) is greater than the critical value of t (t-crit), the hypothesis is rejected otherwise, retained.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between teachers’ professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?

Table 1: Relationship Professional Knowledge and Educational Output

Variables	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
Professional Knowledge (X)	302	3760	3758	49920	49774	48602	0.593
Educational Output (Y)	302						

Field Study, 2023

Result in Table 1 shows the relationship between teachers’ professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. As shown, the r-value is 0.593. This value shows that an average and positive relationship exists between the two variables. This is an indication that the higher the professional knowledge among teachers, the higher the educational output in terms of academic performance among students taught by the teachers.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between teachers’ professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?

Table 2: Relationship Professional Skills and Educational Output

Variables	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
Professional Skills (X)	302						
Educational Output (Y)	302	3776	3758	50148	49774	48760	0.596

Field Study, 2023

Result in Table 2 shows the relationship between teachers’ professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. As shown, the r-value is 0.596. This value shows that an average and positive relationship exists between the two variables. This is an indication that the higher the professional skills among teachers, the higher the educational output in terms of academic performance among students taught by the teachers.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?

Table 3: Relationship professional attitude and conduct and Educational Output

Variables	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
professional attitude and conduct (X)	302	3761	3758	49757	49774	48589	0.603
Educational Output (Y)	302						

Field Study, 2023

Result in Table 3 shows the relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. As shown, the r-value is 0.603. This value shows that a slightly high and positive relationship exists between the two variables. This is an indication that the higher the professional attitude and conduct among teachers, the higher the educational output in terms of academic performance among students taught by the teachers.

Research Question 4: What is the relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis?

Table 4: Relationship professional membership obligations and Educational Output

Variables	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal
professional membership obligations (X)	302	3798	3758	50392	49774	48945	0.599
Educational Output (Y)	302						

Field Study, 2023

Result in Table 4 shows the relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. As shown, the r-value is 0.599. This value shows that an average and positive relationship exists between the two variables. This is an indication that the higher the professional membership obligations among teachers, the higher the educational output in terms of academic performance among students taught by the teachers.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Table 5: Significance of Relationship Professional Knowledge and Educational Output

Variables	N	df	r-cal	z-cal	z-crit	Sig-level	P-value	Decision
Professional Knowledge (X)	302	300	0.593	10.29	1.96	0.05	0.000	Rejected

Educational Output (Y) 302

Field Study, 2023

The result in Table 5 shows the z-transformation for r value. As shown, calculated value of z (z-cal) is 10.29 while the critical value of z (z-crit) is 1.96. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value, the hypothesis was rejected. This shows that there was a significant relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Table 6: Significance of Relationship Professional Skills and Educational Output

Variables	N	df	r-cal	z-cal	z-crit	Sig-level	P-value	Decision
Professional Skills (X)	302	300	0.596	10.34	1.96	0.05	0.000	Rejected
Educational Output (Y)	302							

Field Study, 2023

The result in Table 6 shows the z-transformation for r value. As shown, calculated value of z (z-cal) is 10.34 while the critical value of z (z-crit) is 1.96. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value, the hypothesis was rejected. This shows that there was a significant relationship between teachers' professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Table 7: Significance of Relationship Professional Attitude and Educational Output

Variables	N	df	r-cal	z-cal	z-crit	Sig-level	P-value	Decision
professional attitude and conduct (X)	302	300	0.603	10.47	1.96	0.05	0.000	Rejected
Educational Output (Y)	302							

Field Study, 2023

The result in Table 7 shows the z-transformation for r value. As shown, calculated value of z (z-cal) is 10.47 while the critical value of z (z-crit) is 1.96. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value, the hypothesis was rejected. This shows that there was a significant relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Table 8: Significance of Relationship Professional Membership and Educational Output

Variables	N	df	r-cal	z-cal	z-crit	Sig-level	P-value	Decision
professional membership obligations (X)	302	300	0.599	10.39	1.96	0.05	0.000	Rejected
Educational Output (Y)	302							

Field Study, 2023

The result in Table 7 shows the z-transformation for r value. As shown, calculated value of z (z-cal) is 10.39 while the critical value of z (z-crit) is 1.96. Since the calculated value is greater than the critical value, the hypothesis was rejected. This shows that there was a significant relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one of the studies sought to ascertain the relationship between teachers' professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. The result showed that a positive and a moderate relationship exists between the two variables. The test of significance also indicated that the relationship was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This result was expected and not surprising. Teachers with high professional knowledge in terms of subject matter knowledge could have impacted same to students. The result agrees with the result obtained by Ayeni (2018) that a positive, slightly high and significant relationship existed between teachers' professional ethics and instructional performance of teachers in secondary schools in Owo Local Government, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Research question two of the study sought to ascertain the relationship between teachers' professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. The result showed that a positive and a moderate relationship exists between the two variables. The test of significance also indicated that the relationship was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This result was expected and not surprising. It is expected that teachers with higher professional skill in teaching might influence students' academic performance better than teachers with lower professional skills, hence the result. The result agrees with the result obtained by Chukwu, Ezepue, Evelyn, Iremeka, Onyemaechi, Vivian, & Uwakwe (2020) who found that teachers' professional ethics had a significant relationship with classroom

management and students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Abia State, Nigeria.

Research question three of the study sought to ascertain the relationship between teachers' professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. The result showed that a positive and slightly high relationship exists between the two variables. The test of significance also indicated that the relationship was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This result was expected and not surprising. Teachers who possess acceptable professional attitude and conduct may have demonstrated high level of commitment to duty which may have translated to higher level of academic performance among students. The result agrees with the result obtained by Iroegbu and Uyanga (2019) who found that professional ethics comprising: professional competence, professional integrity and professional accountability significantly predicted quality of educational output in federal universities, South-South Zone of Nigeria.

Research question four, of the study sought to ascertain the relationship between teachers' professional membership obligations and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. The result showed that a positive and moderate relationship exists between the two variables. The test of significance also indicated that the relationship was significant at 0.05 level of significance. This result was expected and not surprising. Teachers who are committed to professional obligations by attending professional meetings such as conferences organized by professional teacher bodies may have gain some experience in terms of practice and theory which they could have employed in their instructional delivery to enhance students' academic performance. The result agrees with the result obtained by Iroegbu and Uyanga (2019) who found that professional ethics comprising: professional competence, professional integrity and professional accountability significantly predicted quality of educational output in federal universities, South-South Zone of Nigeria.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, it can be concluded that a positive, moderate and significant relationship existed between teachers' professional knowledge and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. Similarly, it can also be concluded that a positive, moderate and significant relationship existed between teachers' professional skills and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. Furthermore, it is concluded that a positive, slightly high and significant relationship existed between teachers'

professional attitude and conduct and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis. Finally, it is concluded that a positive, slightly high and significant relationship existed between teachers' professional membership obligation and educational output in secondary schools in Port-Harcourt metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made.

1. School management should ensure teachers possess professional knowledge. During recruitment, only teachers with professional knowledge should be employed into the workforce.
2. School management should ensure teachers possess professional skills. During recruitment, only teachers with professional skills should be recruited into the workforce.
3. School management should ensure teachers possess acceptable professional attitude and conduct.
4. School management should encourage teachers to be committed to professional obligations. This could be achieved by sponsoring teachers to conferences, seminars and workshops organized by professional bodies.

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